

intersection

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Aims and Scope

Intersection welcomes articles detailing qualitative and/or quantitative research on mathematics education, expositions on applications of mathematics education to various fields of endeavor, review of educational resources (print, multimedia, etc), ongoing research project reports, and reflections on the teaching and learning mathematics.

Contributions should be addressed to *Intersection* (c/o MATHTED), Ateneo de Manila University Mathematics Department, Loyola Heights, Quezon City 1108, Philippines. Papers should be double-spaced, with wide margins. Alternatively, send all contributions via electronic mail to cvistro-yu@ateneo.edu. Inquiries may be sent to mathted.intersection@gmail.com.

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From the Editor

One of MATHTED's Special Interest Groups (SIG) is SIG 04: Mathematics Curriculum Enactment (SIG-MCE). Its aim is to provide a venue for its stakeholders to gather and discuss research methods and findings relating to current trends, issues, and developments in mathematics curriculum, its implementation, and learning outcomes. SIG-MCE members strive to: (1) advance content knowledge and skills, pedagogical approaches, and technological tools through research-based mathematics education; (2) share relevant experiences and successful practices in designing and implementing innovative teaching-learning initiatives and strategies; (3) promote collaboration and establish networks that can strengthen curriculum innovations, effective implementation, and successful mathematics learning outcomes.

This first issue of Intersection this year 2025 contains papers that respond to the interests of SIG-MCE. The first paper, *Finetuning Philippine Mathematics Curriculum*, is a project report by Tapani Jussila of Finland who is a long-time consultant for mathematics curriculum projects in the Philippines. He tells his story of helping the "last mile schools" in the country during the COVID-19 pandemic starting in the year 2021. The goal of the curriculum project was to modernize and diversify Philippine high school study materials by applying suitable learning technologies and strengthening the local teaching staff with new and upgraded skills. Bermejo's reflection paper, *Reflections on Realistic Mathematics Education: Reimagining the Philippine Mathematics Classroom through Insights from the Netherlands*, is a timeless piece. Based on the author's experience of Utrecht Summer School on Mathematics Education back in August 2019, the insights offered are worthy of serious discussions by advocates of Realistic Mathematics Education or RME with those who are keenly interested in pursuing it. Bermejo's dreams and aspirations for a mathematics curriculum that captures the essences of RME are certainly well-placed. She must be heard. Perez's research paper, *The Effectiveness of Flipped-Classroom Model on Mathematics Performance: Basis for a Proposed Learning Plan*, offers an enlightened investigation on the use flipped classrooms, which was gaining popularity until the pandemic hit the world. Compared to the traditional classroom model, the flipped classroom model revealed positive outcomes related to students' understanding of the lessons, class discussions, students' engagement and learning, and collaboration among students. As with any innovative pedagogical approach, there were challenges encountered by students that the study found. The last paper for this issue is an enlightening piece that describes in detail a learning environment that takes students outside the four walls of the classroom. In Ludwig's paper, *MathCityMap – Math Trails in the Digital Age*, details of his plenary presentation at MATHTED 2025: 15th Biennial and International Conference are provided. Due to the demand for mathematics to be connected to students' realities, the trend to do mathematics outside – often found under the catchword "*outdoor mathematics*" seems to be gaining ground. His paper discusses how Math Trails might be able to satisfy the demand and provide ideas for a learning environment that responds to the concern to have a relatable mathematics for students.

Certainly, mathematics education research (MER) has become much more exciting in the recent years. This would not have been possible without the efforts of MATHTED to encourage the submission of high-quality papers stemming from significant research. We call on all MER enthusiasts to work with MATHTED's SIGs. We see a bright future as more and more young researchers are finding their way to be active and make a significant contribution to the field.

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Reflections on Realistic Mathematics Education: Reimagining the Philippine Mathematics Classroom through Insights from The Netherlands

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Abstract

This paper presents a reflective account of my participation in the Utrecht Summer School on Mathematics Education, held from August 19 to 30, 2019, at Utrecht University in the Netherlands. Organized by the Freudenthal Institute, the program focused on Realistic Mathematics Education (RME)—a Dutch approach that views mathematics as a human activity grounded in meaningful, real-world contexts. As a Filipino educator, I joined the program to explore research-based strategies that could inform more engaging and effective math teaching in the Philippines. The Summer School brought together participants from diverse backgrounds, fostering rich discussions and collaborative learning. Sessions addressed a range of topics including curriculum design, contextualized modeling and assessment, and the role of technology in math education. Insights from Dutch experts provided a deeper understanding of how RME principles are applied in practice. Experiencing RME firsthand prompted a critical reflection on the contrast between Dutch and Filipino mathematics education. While the Philippine system often emphasizes memorization and procedural fluency, RME offers a more student-centered, inquiry-based model that encourages conceptual understanding and real-life problem solving. Despite challenges such as curriculum rigidity and limited resources, the adaptability of RME holds promise for local implementation. This reflection highlights key lessons from the Summer School and considers how RME can inform teacher education, curriculum development, and classroom practices in the Philippines. The experience reaffirmed my commitment to making mathematics more meaningful, accessible, and engaging for Filipino learners, and underscored the value of international collaboration in advancing educational reform.

Introduction

This reflection paper examines the Realistic Mathematics Education (RME) approach as developed and implemented in the Netherlands, critically assessing its potential for localization within the Philippine educational context. Drawing upon insights gained from a recent summer school experience, the paper compares the educational systems of the Philippines and the Netherlands. Additionally, it explores how RME principles can be integrated into lesson design to enhance mathematics instruction for Filipino students.

This paper is organized into several key sections to guide the reader through the discussion. It begins with First Impression and Environment, followed by an Understanding of Realistic Mathematics Education and its role in Dutch Mathematics Education. Insights from Meaningful Workshops and Learning are then presented. The paper continues with a reflection through a Filipino perspective, exploring Educational Culture and Systemic Realities in the Philippine Context. It addresses the Challenges in Localizing Realistic Mathematics Education and discusses Opportunities and Plans for Implementation in Filipino Classrooms. The paper concludes with Personal and Professional Realizations, the

integration of RME into the Philippine educational landscape, and final reflections.

First Impression and Environment

The Utrecht Summer School on Realistic Mathematics Education (RME) is an annual international program organized by the Freudenthal Institute at Utrecht University, in the Netherlands. Known for its emphasis on innovative and research-based approaches to mathematics education, the summer school brings together educators, researchers, and graduate students from around the world to explore the principles and applications of RME—a pedagogical theory that positions mathematics as a meaningful, human activity grounded in real-life contexts.

As a graduate student in Mathematics Education in the Philippines, I joined the summer school with a keen interest in exploring how the RME framework could inform and strengthen my own research, particularly in the context of my dissertation. My goal was to gain a deeper understanding of how RME can be adapted to the Philippine educational setting, and to examine how the Dutch perspective on mathematics education could offer valuable insights

into creating more relevant and engaging learning experiences for Filipino students.

This reflection presents my personal experiences and professional learnings from the program. It highlights key ideas from RME that resonated with me, as well as critical insights into how these concepts might be applied or reimaged within the unique challenges and opportunities of mathematics education in the Philippines.

Arriving in Utrecht was both an exciting and humbling experience. Known for its rich academic tradition and vibrant cultural atmosphere, the city immediately struck me as a place where history and innovation coexist harmoniously. Cruising through its scenic streets and walking past centuries-old buildings gave a sense of both calm and intellectual curiosity—an atmosphere that was mirrored within Utrecht University itself. The university campus exuded a quiet energy, with open spaces that encouraged thoughtful discussion and collaborative learning.

From the very first day, the international nature of the summer school became one of its most enriching aspects. Adding a layer of personal meaning to the experience was the fact that I was the only Filipino in the batch. This brought with it a deep sense of pride—representing my country on an international academic stage—but also a subtle pressure to do well, to contribute meaningfully, and to bring a unique voice to the table. It became a quiet but constant motivation to engage fully and thoughtfully in every discussion. Michiel Doorman, the course coordinator, warmly welcomed all participants, setting a collegial and inclusive tone for the days ahead. I had the opportunity to interact with fellow participants from various countries—teachers, researchers, and graduate students from Europe, Asia, Africa, and South America. Each brought their own unique perspective shaped by their cultural and educational contexts. These conversations, both inside and outside the classroom, deepened my appreciation for the global relevance of mathematics education and the many ways in which RME can be interpreted and adapted.

The learning environment was open, inclusive, and highly interactive. Sessions were structured not just as lectures but as opportunities for dialogue and exploration. We were encouraged to question, reflect, and connect theory to practice. The facilitators modeled the very principles of RME—valuing student input, building on prior knowledge, and using real-life contexts to ground abstract concepts. This culture of open exchange fostered a sense of community and intellectual curiosity, where everyone's voice was heard and respected.

Understanding Realistic Mathematics Education

RME is a domain-specific instructional approach developed in the Netherlands in 1971. Originating

from a problem-based perspective on mathematics education, RME has since evolved into one of the most detailed and influential pedagogical frameworks in the field. Although it has been in practice for nearly five decades, RME continues to be regarded by its proponents—particularly in the Netherlands—as a work in progress, constantly refined through ongoing research and classroom experience.

The impact of RME on mathematics education is substantial, largely due to its defining characteristics. Central to the approach is the emphasis on “realistic” situations as a foundation for learning. These situations serve as meaningful contexts in which students can develop mathematical concepts, tools, procedures, and understanding. Importantly, in the RME framework, the term “realistic” goes beyond simply referring to real-world scenarios. Rooted in the Dutch expression “zich realiseren”, meaning “to imagine,” realistic situations are those that students can mentally visualize and relate to, whether drawn from reality or the imagination (Van den Heuvel-Panhuizen & Drijvers, 2014).

RME is deeply influenced by the ideas of Hans Freudenthal (1973, 1991), who asserted that mathematics should be taught as a relevant, meaningful, and human activity. As such, learning mathematics should also be a social process, where students construct knowledge through guided interaction with real or imagined contexts. As Streefland (1993) notes, “realistic” in RME refers not only to the authenticity of a context but also to the learner's process of realization—how they personally experience and make sense of mathematical ideas.

Rather than relying solely on externally imposed content, RME engages students' existing knowledge and intuitive thinking, encouraging them to construct meaning, make connections among concepts, and gradually develop more abstract understanding. By grounding learning in realistic contexts, RME supports the development of mathematical competence that is both meaningful and applicable to real-world situations. Central to this approach is the use of carefully designed tasks that guide students in transitioning from informal, intuitive understandings to more formal mathematical thinking. The design of these tasks is informed by the core principles of RME:

1. Didactical phenomenology – identifying phenomena that can be mathematically organized.
2. Emergent models – using models that evolve from students' informal strategies to more formal mathematical representations.
3. Guided reinvention – allowing students to rediscover mathematical concepts through structured, exploratory experiences.

As RME emphasizes making mathematics meaningful by connecting it to real-world contexts, a key concept in achieving this is recognizing the

distinction between *horizontal* and *vertical mathematization* (Van den Heuvel-Panhuizen & Drijvers, 2014). Horizontal mathematization involves students translating real-life situations into mathematical representations, thereby linking everyday experiences to mathematical thinking. In contrast, vertical mathematization focuses on developing and refining mathematical ideas through reasoning, structuring, and abstraction. This distinction underscores the importance of designing learning experiences that support both types of mathematization, enabling students to engage with mathematics meaningfully while also progressing toward deeper conceptual understanding.

RME in the Dutch Mathematics Education

RME is implemented throughout the Dutch education system, from primary to tertiary levels. At the primary level, mathematics is introduced through real-world contexts that are meaningfully real to students (Treffers, 1991). For instance, students might explore the transportation system by applying "hop on-hop off" concepts on a series of addition and subtraction operations.

In secondary schools, the principles of RME are extended to more formal and abstract notions while remaining grounded in real-life problems. Emphasis is placed on modeling, progressive formalization, multiple solution strategies, and fostering discourse and reflection through open-ended questions (Gravemeijer, 1994).

Although RME was initially developed for primary schools, its influence extends into teacher education programs and some university-level applied mathematics and vocational courses. Furthermore, RME is utilized to train future educators to design learning environments that support mathematical reasoning and student-centered learning (van den Heuvel-Panhuizen, 2003).

Meaningful Workshops and Learning Insights

There were several engaging workshops throughout the program, but I was particularly looking forward to the day dedicated entirely to *Assessment*. Given its central role in shaping effective teaching and learning in mathematics, this focus felt especially relevant and timely. The day featured a series of lectures that explored assessment from various angles, each offering valuable insights into how we can better understand and support students' mathematical development. The day began with Paul Drijvers, who spoke on *Two Assessment Challenges: Digital Assessment and Mathematical Thinking*. His session tackled the evolving landscape of assessment in the digital age, exploring how technology can support—not replace—the assessment of deeper mathematical reasoning.

Next, Michiel Veldhuis delivered a particularly impactful session titled *Classroom Assessment*. His

talk stood out to me for its practical and thought-provoking approach. Veldhuis emphasized that assessment should be more than a grading tool—it should actively inform instruction and support learning. He highlighted how good assessment identifies where students are in their understanding and helps guide them forward. It should stimulate thinking, be inclusive and accessible, and reveal different levels of reasoning. He framed assessment broadly—as *everything that allows teachers to gather information about students' understanding*—positioning it as an integral part of quality math instruction.

Following that, Mieke Abels gave a lecture titled *Assessment: What and How*, prompting important reflection on what we choose to assess and the methods we use. She emphasized aligning assessments with learning goals and being intentional about how we interpret and act on assessment data. The day concluded with Sietske Tacoma, who explored *Automated Feedback in Statistics Education*. Her session demonstrated how technology, when thoughtfully applied, can offer timely, formative feedback that supports students in statistical reasoning and self-correction.

Another particularly fruitful day of the program centered around the theme of *Learning by Problem Solving*. The sessions during this day not only deepened our understanding of problem-solving as a pedagogical approach but also provided hands-on experiences that challenged our own thinking. The day began with a lecture by Marjolein Kool on *TORPEDO: A Digital Learning Environment to Develop Problem-Solving Ability in Primary Teacher Training*. The session showcased how digital tools can be effectively integrated into teacher education to foster problem-solving skills. TORPEDO serves as a platform where prospective teachers engage in open-ended, meaningful mathematical problems, encouraging them to think flexibly and reflectively.

This was followed by a lively and curious working group activity titled "*Is a Smooth Slope to Slide a Smooth Slide to Slope?*" led by Rogier Bos. Though I approached it with some initial hesitation, the session turned out to be incredibly engaging. The task encouraged us to explore a deceptively simple mathematical situation through multiple lenses—drawing on spatial reasoning, communication, and collaboration. One key observation I took away was that while the preparation for such problem-solving tasks can be time-consuming, the outcomes—when executed well—are genuinely thought-provoking. These activities not only stimulate deep mathematical thinking but also offer rich opportunities for discussion, creativity, and critical reflection.

One lecture that resonated deeply with me was "*The Relevance of Language in Mathematics Education*" by Dolly van Eerde and Monica Wijers.

This session touched on a topic that often goes unnoticed in mathematics education: the powerful role of language in shaping understanding. The speakers emphasized the importance of distinguishing between mathematical language and the general language used by students. Language serves both social and individual functions in the classroom, and recognizing this dual role is essential for effective teaching. They reminded us that every school subject has its own specialized language, but mathematics stands out due to the abstract and symbolic nature of its discourse. This uniqueness demands that teachers become not only proficient in mathematics but also sensitive to how students access and express mathematical ideas through language. A quote shared during the lecture, originally by Hans Freudenthal (1984), beautifully captured the essence of the discussion:

"If it comes to language – an important but not the only aspect of school and life – one would call the combination of the subjects mathematics and mother tongue ideal for future teachers."

Altogether, the workshops provided a rich and meaningful learning experience leaving a strong impression. The day focused on *assessment* stood out for highlighting the importance of addressing both horizontal (real-world application) and vertical (conceptual depth and progression) goals, emphasizing that effective assessment supports deeper, student-centered learning. The focus on *problem-solving* further reinforced its value—not just as a learning outcome, but as a powerful teaching approach that fosters engagement and critical thinking, despite requiring careful preparation. A particularly impactful session on the *relevance of language in mathematics education* emphasized that language should be seen as a bridge rather than a barrier, enabling more inclusive and effective communication of mathematical ideas. These themes—assessment, problem-solving, and language—are deeply interconnected; together they shape a more thoughtful, holistic approach to teaching mathematics.

Reflecting Through a Filipino Lens: Resonance and Realities

As a Filipino educator, encountering RME felt both affirming and challenging. Its core ideas—like seeing math as a human activity rooted in context—resonated deeply with my own beliefs about meaningful learning. At the same time, observing how RME is practiced in the Netherlands highlighted key cultural and systemic differences that made me reflect on what real reform would require back home.

Educational Culture and Systemic Realities in the Philippine Context

One of the most striking realizations during the summer school was how RME differs from the traditional approach to mathematics education in the Philippines—both in philosophy and classroom practice. In the Philippines, mathematics is often taught in a procedural and teacher-centered manner (though several reforms are now working). The focus is typically on mastering algorithms, memorizing formulas, and getting the "right answer." Lessons tend to follow a rigid structure: a teacher explains a procedure, students take notes, and then they solve practice problems that mirror what was just taught. Real-world application or conceptual development is sometimes included, but it is often an afterthought rather than an integral part of the lesson.

Culturally, Philippine classrooms tend to emphasize hierarchy, with students expected to follow rather than question. In the Netherlands, I saw a more open, dialogic approach where teachers valued students' ideas, even if it meant temporary confusion. This made me realize that adopting RME isn't just about new methods—it requires a shift in classroom culture. By contrast, RME promotes a learner-centered and context-driven approach. It begins with meaningful problems set in realistic contexts that students can imagine or relate to. These problems are not used merely to illustrate a concept, but as starting points for mathematical exploration and sense-making. Instead of simply receiving information, students are encouraged to develop strategies, create models, and discuss their reasoning with others. The teacher's role shifts from instructor to facilitator—guiding reinvention rather than delivering content.

Differences between the Philippines and the Netherlands extend beyond the classroom to their broader educational and societal structures. In the Philippines, a heavy emphasis on standardized testing and national assessments often results in a backwash effect that limits deeper mathematical understanding (Sabio et al., 2015). Additionally, societal pressures contribute to widespread math anxiety among Filipino students (Nolasco, 2025), fostering an environment where questioning and experimentation are discouraged. Hierarchical classroom dynamics further impact students' self-assessment and engagement. As a study by Nacion (2017) found for example, students who scored higher often felt a sense of superiority over their peers, reinforcing classroom stratification. This reality sharply contrasts with the Dutch RME philosophy, which promotes guided reinvention, collective sense-making, and active student participation.

Another key difference lies in how RME values student thinking and informal strategies. In the Philippine classroom, there is often a single "correct"

method, and students may feel discouraged from thinking outside the standard process. In RME, however, multiple solution paths are welcomed, and students' intuitive ideas are seen as valid steppingstones toward formal mathematics. This approach not only enhances conceptual understanding but also builds student confidence and ownership of learning.

These differences made me reflect deeply on the potential of RME to address some of the persistent issues in Philippine math education—such as student disengagement, rote learning, and math anxiety. While challenges in implementation would certainly exist, RME offers a compelling alternative that puts understanding, context, and student agency at the heart of mathematics learning.

Challenges in Localizing Realistic Mathematics Education

Implementing Realistic Mathematics Education (RME) in the Philippines presents several challenges. A primary issue is teacher preparedness, as educators must have a deep understanding of RME's core principles. Another significant challenge lies in assessment, specifically, in training teachers and aligning evaluations with RME's open-ended principles. The Dutch model relies on these evaluations to capture both conceptual understanding and formal mathematical knowledge. Finally, policy resistance within the educational system poses a significant barrier; systemic change is often met with reluctance rather than support.

Embracing RME in the Filipino Classroom: Opportunities and Plans for Implementation

While there are undeniable challenges to implementing RME in the Philippine context, there are also unique strengths within Filipino classrooms that offer promising opportunities for its application. Filipino students naturally thrive in collaborative settings. Peer discussions, group work, and a shared sense of community are already present in many classrooms, aligning well with RME's emphasis on learning through social interaction and dialogue. By tapping into these existing dynamics, RME-based tasks can foster deeper engagement and collective sense-making.

Another key strength is the creativity and storytelling ability of Filipino learners (Cerna et al., 2025). RME encourages students to engage in real-life situations and to bring their own experiences into the learning process. Filipino students are often adept at drawing connections between classroom concepts and their everyday lives—whether through local market scenarios, family budgeting, or community issues. These culturally relevant and meaningful contexts provide fertile ground for designing rich, realistic tasks that can help students

understand and appreciate the role of mathematics in their world.

Filipino teachers, too, bring an important asset to the table: adaptability. Despite constraints such as large class sizes or limited resources, many educators demonstrate resilience and creativity in finding ways to support student learning (Perez, Valera, & Limos-Galay, 2023). This resourcefulness is invaluable when implementing RME, which doesn't rely on expensive materials but instead centers on meaningful, student-driven exploration of real-world problems.

Recognizing these opportunities, I began integrating RME principles into my teaching in my own small way by crafting and embedding context-rich problems into my lessons—drawing from local examples and encouraging students to create scenarios based on their own lived experiences. I shifted my classroom approach to be more student-centered by fostering dialogue, promoting group projects, and facilitating collaborative problem-solving activities. These modest yet meaningful adjustments had a noticeable impact, empowering students to take greater ownership of their learning and helping them see mathematics as more accessible and relevant.

Beyond my own classroom, I hope to contribute to a broader movement of promoting RME in the Philippines. Through workshops and professional learning communities, I aim to share what I have learned from the Utrecht Summer School and help other educators see how RME can be thoughtfully adapted to our local context. Importantly, designing tasks through the lens of RME is not a rigid process—it allows for flexibility, creativity, and cultural sensitivity. It encourages teachers to value their students' backgrounds and everyday realities, making math education not only more meaningful but also more inclusive.

As part of this effort, I have also developed a research instrument aligned with RME's core ideas, which I hope will provide valuable insights into how these approaches work in Filipino classrooms. By contributing to the growing body of knowledge around RME—especially in the Philippine setting—I aim to support both practical application and academic understanding of how context-based, student-centered learning can truly make a difference. Ultimately, I believe that embracing RME offers a chance to rethink how we teach mathematics—grounding it in real life, making it collaborative, and centering students in the learning process. With the cultural strengths already present in Filipino classrooms, there's great potential for these ideas to take root and thrive.

Implementing RME in the Philippines will not be easy. Challenges like large class sizes, limited time, high stakes testing, and lack of training or resources can make student-centered learning difficult. But I believe small, intentional changes—like using open-

ended problems, encouraging student thinking, and drawing from everyday Filipino contexts—can start to shift perspectives. RME does not have to be copied exactly as it is. What matters is adapting its core philosophy in ways that make sense to our students and classrooms—grounded in local culture, experiences, and realities.

Personal and Professional Realizations

Attending the Utrecht Summer School on Realistic Mathematics Education was more than just an academic endeavor—it was a transformative learning experience that reshaped the way I see mathematics teaching and learning. Coming from a background where math is often taught in a fixed, procedural way, I found myself deeply challenged and inspired by the philosophy of RME and the way it was thoughtfully integrated into every aspect of the program.

One of the most profound reaffirmations in my perspective was recognizing that mathematics does not have to begin with rules—it can begin with life. The use of context-rich problems showed me how students can engage more meaningfully when math is tied to situations they can relate to, imagine, or even create. This concept moved me beyond the traditional view that real-life applications come *after* learning the concept, and toward the idea that real-life situations can be the very foundation of mathematical thinking.

The emphasis on student-centered learning—where the teacher is a facilitator, not just a transmitter of knowledge—also struck a chord in me. Watching how students' informal strategies were validated and built upon through guided reinvention made me reflect on how often we, as educators, unintentionally limit our students by predefining the "correct" path. The summer school reminded me that learning happens best when students are allowed to explore, struggle, and reason in their own ways—with guidance that respects their thinking.

Beyond the theoretical and pedagogical tools, I left the summer school with a renewed sense of purpose and responsibility—to not only pursue these ideas in my research but to advocate for a more meaningful, human-centered approach to mathematics education in the Philippines. It reminded me that transformation in education begins with transformed educators.

Integrating RME in the Philippine Educational Landscape

Adopting RME in the Philippines represents a significant shift in mathematics instruction. This approach aligns with the Department of Education's emphasis on developing 21st-century skills such as critical thinking, collaboration, and problem-solving. These competencies are embedded in the core principles of RME, which positions learners at the

center of instruction and situates learning within meaningful, real-world contexts.

This paradigm shift demands that curriculum planning must move away from rigid, content-heavy approaches toward more flexible and concept-driven designs that are responsive to real-life situations. This also requires the development of innovative teaching strategies that emphasize guided reinvention, student collaboration, and mathematical discourse -- marking a departure from traditional, procedural methods.

In terms of assessment, RME emphasizes open-ended and formative tasks that aim to capture students' reasoning and understanding, rather than focusing solely on correct answers. To effectively implement this approach, teachers require comprehensive training that covers the philosophy and pedagogy of RME, as well as effective classroom management strategies. This shift goes beyond pedagogy; it also involves a transformation in teachers' beliefs about teaching and learning. Embracing this change allows educators to better respond to the needs of Filipino learners, who benefit from contextualized instruction, real-life relevance, and opportunities for reflective learning.

Ultimately, integrating RME addresses long-standing issues in Philippine mathematics education, particularly students' disengagement and surface-level learning. By promoting deeper mathematical understanding, RME helps reduce mathematical illiteracy and empowers students through meaningful learning experiences. This approach marks a shift in educational priorities from memorization to understanding, from routine tasks to real-world relevance, and from lesson-centered teaching to learner-centered instruction. On a broader scale, RME has the potential to bridge gaps in current educational practices, encourage the practical application of mathematics, and build students' confidence in using mathematics in their daily lives.

Conclusion

Looking back at my experience in the Utrecht Summer School on Realistic Mathematics Education, I am filled with a deep sense of gratitude and renewed purpose. The two weeks I spent immersed in the RME framework, surrounded by passionate educators and researchers from around the world, have left a lasting impact—not only on my academic journey but also on my identity as an educator. I leave with a clearer vision of what mathematics education can and should be: contextual, meaningful, student-driven, and rooted in the real lives of learners.

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to the organizers, facilitators, and the entire team at the Freudenthal Institute for creating a rich and supportive learning environment. Their openness, expertise, and generosity made this experience truly

transformative. I am equally thankful to my fellow participants, whose diverse perspectives and thoughtful conversations expanded my worldview and reminded me that education is, at its core, a collective endeavor.

As I return to the Philippines, I carry with me not only new knowledge and tools but also a renewed hope—that change is possible, even in the most traditional of classrooms. I envision a future where Filipino students learn mathematics not just to pass exams, but to understand, to explore, and to connect with the world around them. As Hans Freudenthal once said,

“Mathematics must be connected to reality, stay close to children, and be relevant to society.”

This vision, I believe, is both necessary and within reach. Planting the seeds of RME in our classrooms may take time, but with care, collaboration, and commitment, they will grow. And with them, so will a generation of learners who see mathematics not as a mystery to fear but as a powerful tool to make sense of their world.

Final Thoughts

Reflecting on my time at the summer school, I can honestly say it was one of the most enriching academic experiences I have had. For anyone curious, motivated, or just eager to explore, I highly encourage you to consider applying to the next edition. You won't regret it. You can check out the link:

<https://utrechtsummerschool.nl/courses/science/mathematics-and-science-education>

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Appendix

"Kicking off an exciting journey of learning and growth — Summer School begins!"

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